

Fault Detection and Tolerance in Cluster of Workstations using Message Passing Interface

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Abstract— A Cluster of Workstations (COW) is network based multi-computer system aimed to replace supercomputers. A cluster of workstations works on Divisible Load Theory (DLT) according to which a job is divided into n subtasks and delegated to n workstations in the COW architecture. To get the job completed, all subtasks must be completed. Therefore, for satisfactory job completion, all workstations must be functional. However, a faulty node can suspend the overall job completion task until and unless some fault avoidance and correction measures are taken. This paper presents a fault detection and fault tolerant algorithm which will use Message Passing Interface (MPI) to identify faulty workstations and transfer the subtask being performed by them to a normally working workstation. The assigned workstations will continue their original subtasks in addition to assigned subtasks on time sharing basis.

Received: January 21, 2011, Accepted: February 22, 2011

Index Terms— Availability, Cluster of Workstation, MPI Applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of powerful workstations and high speed network solutions has made Cluster of Workstations (COW) as attractive alternative to expansive supercomputers. It has been observed that COW can be compared with the supercomputers for some applications [1]. Example of such COW systems include: IBM SP2, DEC TruCluster, Hp, Intel/Sandia etc. According to Pfister, over 100,000 computer clusters are in use worldwide [2]. Besides handling large computational workloads, COWs provide high availability and scalability features.

A cluster of workstation is based upon Divisible Load Theory (DLT). According to divisible load theory, the computation and communication loads are partitioned arbitrarily among a number of processors and links [3]. The only requirement for DLT is non data dependency. This approach of load distribution applied to the processing of very large data files in signal processing, image processing, experimental data processing and grid computing. In this paradigm, a job is submitted to a root node, which breaks the task into n subtasks and delegates to n workstations. Each workstation returns its sub result to the root node, which combines all sub results and declare the task completed. A job cannot be declared as completed until all subtasks are completed by the participating workstations. The features of fault tolerance in COWs must be injected to avoid overall task failures. In this paper we present a fault tolerant scheme for COWs, in which a normally working workstation node can take over the subtask assigned to a failed workstation node. Rest of the paper is organized as follows: section II explains the proposed algorithm and its implementation. Section III presents the availability modeling of a COW incorporating the proposed algorithm and the conclusion is presented in section IV.

II. PROPOSED FAULT TOLERANT ALGORITHM FOR COW

A COW is a distributed memory system based upon shared no-thing architecture. A COW System consists of a root node and n workstations (WS) connected by a network as shown in fig. 1.

Fig. 1: COW Architecture

A job is submitted to the root node, which partitions the job according to an algorithm and distributed the sub loads to n workstations. Individual workstations are supposed to complete their subtask and return their results to the root workstation. However, the faults in workstations will degrade the performance of COW because the overall job completion cannot be declared completed. Some researchers have addressed the issue of faults in COW [4-5]. As a solution for achieving fault tolerance in COW, the idea of introducing redundant backup workstations was presented by Sameer in [4]. In this solution, a workstation performs periodic checkpoint its results on a backup node. If the node goes down, the backup node captures the role of the failed node. It may be observed that as individual workstations are working independently, they are equally vulnerable to intermittent or permanent failures. The solution suggested

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by Sameer is, therefore, costly because each workstation in COW cannot be attached with redundant backup node.

A. Proposed Algorithm

According to our proposed scheme, the root node (RN) can monitor the performance of all workstations by sending periodic diagnostic or so called “health check” messages to them. Each workstation is bound to respond to the health check message within a predefined time interval. If the expected message is not received from a workstation, the root node will mark it as “faulty” and will redistribute its subtask to any surviving workstation in the system. The assigned node will carry on the newly assigned subtask in addition to its originally assigned subtask.

According to the proposed fault tolerant scheme, all the subtasks assigned to n workstations can still be considered completed if at least one workstation in the system is in not faulty. This phenomenon is cogent because the multiprocessing operating system running on each workstation can run n subtasks with degraded performance. Let p be the probability of working of a workstation then the probability of one workstation failure will be $1-p$ and the probability of all workstation failures (F) can be estimated as [6]:

$$F = (1 - p)^N \quad (1)$$

The probability of at least one workstation’s survival (S) will be:

$$S = 1 - (1 - p)^N \quad (2)$$

In other words, we can conclude that with the proposed fault tolerant algorithm, probability of a task completion with n workstations will be $1 - (1 - p)^N$.

To implement the proposed fault diagnostic algorithm, RN uses a variable called Workstation Index (WINDX), which points to an i th surviving workstation at a given instance of time. To detect the failure in a workstation, RN runs following steps:

- Root node sends diagnostic messages periodically to a workstations indicated by WINDX
- If an i th workstation is not faulty, it will respond back to the RN with an acknowledgment message within a predefined time interval
- If root node does not receive acknowledgment from a node, it will assume it faulty
- Root node redistribute the subtask of faulty node to a surviving node, which will continue its originally assigned subtask

The steps of the fault tolerant algorithm may be summarized in the flow chart shown in fig 2. Root node continuously repeats the fault detection and fault tolerant algorithm. WINDX is initialized by pointing to the first workstation in

the system and continuously updated until it reaches to point to the last workstation in COW system.

B. Fault Tolerant Algorithm Implementation

A COW is distributed memory architecture of workstations connected to the same network. The root node can communicate with remote workstations by following some message passing protocol. The best choice for this communication is Message Passing Interface (MPI) [7]. MPI is a communications protocol used for sending or receiving data or messages between networked workstations. MPI’s point-to-point communication routines can be utilized to implement Fault Tolerant Algorithm proposed in this paper.

MPI supports blocking and non-blocking send/receive routines to send various classes of data types among multiple workstations. To send data the sender node needs the id of the destination workstation. Each workstation in COW may acquire a unique id by launching a parallel programming environment such as LAM-MPI [8]. LAM-MPI developed at Ohio Supercomputer Center is a parallel programming environment for networked computers in COW.

Fig. 2: Fault Detection and Tolerant Algorithm executed by root node

In our proposed fault tolerant algorithm, the root node sends diagnostic messages to each workstation by using MPI non-blocking MPI send routines. Contrast to blocking MPI send routine, the non-blocking MPI send routine immediately returns to the sending process at root node. The root node cannot use blocking MPI send routine because in case of a failed node, the send routine will block the whole diagnostic

process due to infinite wait for the response from the failed node. On the other hand, a non-blocking send will immediately return to the sender process despite of the response from the destination workstation. In order to detect the outcome of the MPI non-blocking send, MPI_Test routine can be used. The syntax of MPI_Test is shown below [7]:

```
int MPI_Test(MPI_Request *request, int *flag, MPI_Status *status) (3)
```

In expression (3) “request” is a structure of type MPI_Request. This structure is used to determine the outcome of MPI’s non-blocking send. If MPI_Test is followed by non-blocking send, it assigns “true” to the variable “flag” for a successful non-blocking send operation. In this situation, the value of “request” is set to MPI_REQUEST_NULL. On the other hand, if the non-blocking send routine is incomplete, MPI_Test routine will assign “false” to the variable “flag” and the value of “request” remains unchanged. The suggested diagnostic algorithm running at the root node can try this process for sometime before it decides the target node is down or up. If the “flag” variable remains “false” for some pre-determined time interval, then the root node will mark it as faulty. It will then assign the subtasks of the faulty node to any surviving node in the system.

C. Rollback and Check pointing

In order to implement the proposed fault tolerant architecture, we assume, the COW architecture can be attributed with a check pointing mechanism which allows periodic saving of the process in a storage area[9 - 10]. When a faulty node is identified, the root node transfers the pointers of failed nodes’ process state (stored in the storage) to the newly assigned node for the rollback. To implement this rollback mechanism, the root node maintains a database of pointers of check pointing in the storage for each process running on all workstations in COW.

D. Fault Tolerance in Root Node

The root node performs supervisory and diagnostic role, its failure will be catastrophic to overall function of the COW architecture. To make root node fault tolerant, we suggest, RN can be paired with another workstation in “mutual takeover” configuration as shown in fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Root Node and its backup with heartbeat protocol

The Root node and back node can monitor each other by using “heartbeat” protocol [11]. The heartbeat protocol is implemented by sending a special message to another machine on regular basis. When the “heartbeat” message is not received from the other machine, it is assumed to be failed. In

this situation, the backup node will resume the tasks of RN.

III. AVAILABILITY MODELING

Availability is an important performance parameter used to determine the probability of a system’s accessibility at an instant of time *t* [12]. Misbahuddin and Al-Holou have developed availability model for high performance multi-computer systems with high availability solutions [6]. This model can be manipulated for estimating the Availability of the fault tolerant COW system suggested in this paper.

The availability of COW of size N workstations can be estimated by considering the availabilities of individual workstation nodes. A workstation node is said to be available as long as it is either in state *S*₀ or in state *S*₁. A workstation is in state *S*₀ if it is performing its original subtasks only and it is in *S*₁ if it is performing its original assignment along with the subtask of a failed node [6]. According to the suggested fault tolerant algorithm, the number of workstations in *S*₁ will be equal to the number of failed workstation (*N*_{*f*}) because for each failed workstation, one surviving server node will switch to *S*₁ state. In this situation, *N* - 2*N*_{*f*} workstations will be in single operational mode or normally working states (*S*₀). If *P*(*S*₀) and *P*(*S*₁) be the state probabilities of workstation being in state *S*₀ or state *S*₁, then the system availability expression for COW can be written as:

$$A = [(P(S_1)^{N_f})] [(P(S_0)^{(N-N_f)})] \tag{4}$$

For the purpose of comparison, availability has been calculated for two COW systems: one with fault tolerant solutions and second without fault tolerant solution. fig. 4-5 shows the graphical relationship between failure rates and the availabilities for COW with and without proposed fault tolerant solutions. These results show the availability of the systems attributed with high available solution (running fault tolerant algorithm) decreases slowly compared to the systems without high availability solutions with increasing failure rates of workstations.

Fig. 5: Availability Vs Failure rate for COW of 4 workstations

Fig. 6: Availability Vs Failure rate for COW of 8 Workstations

Fig. 7: Availability Vs Failure rate for COW of 16 Workstations

IV. CONCLUSION

A Cluster of workstation (COW) is an ensemble of homogenous or heterogeneous low cost computing machines connected to a high speed network. COWs are intended to replace costly supercomputers. COWs can give an illusion of a single computer machine to solve one common problem. However, this single machine image of COW is impaired when one or more component workstations' fail in the system. This paper has shown the application of MPI non-blocking point-to-point communication routines to implement the proposed fault identification and tolerant algorithm. The algorithm allows a normally working workstation to replace a faulty workstation. Therefore, no redundant backup workstations are needed. Numerical results show that the algorithm improves the workstation availability to the assigned tasks by assigning the tasks of the failed workstations to the normally working workstations.

V. REFERENCES

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